

METHODS OF ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT STUDY OF STUDENTS IN THE CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM

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Annotation. This article analyzes the issues of organizing independent study of students in the credit-module system and develops practical recommendations.

Keywords. FAQ, forum, test solution, colloquium, case study, glossary, link, chart, Q/A, review, SWOT, interview.

The independent work of the students (IWS) is a student's specific learning activity, which is aimed at independently performing didactic tasks, interested in studyingtishga and increasing knowledge in a particular field of science. The content of TMI will be associated with the performance of practical tasks that allow to formulate logical thinking, creative activity, research approach in the mastering of the teaching material. Usually IWS includes the independent work of the student (Ormi) under the guidance of the teacher, which is carried out outside the audience, together with the full independent work of the student.

In the form of daytime training, the total hours of IWS in bakalavriat are half the volume of the fan, and also almost half of it is allocated to the mid-term. In correspondence education, it is desirable that the volume of IWS is 4/5 part of the volume of science.

The ORIWS workload is not entirely part of the teacher's workload, but for the contact classes the teacher is assigned a separate workload (calculation work, course work, course project, graduation work, master's dissertation, research supervisor's guide, basic doctoral student's guide, etc.).

The organization of IWS is carried out in accordance with the requirements of the main normative documents of the university, including the working curriculum (syllabus), the independent study of science modules.

IWS can be implemented in the following forms:

- types of independent work performed directly by the student on a mobile device;
- Independent student work under the guidance of a traditional teacher;
- Independent student work under the guidance of an electronic teacher.
- Types of independent work that can be done directly by the student via a mobile device

include:

- Preparation for the lesson - study of lecture notes, vodkas, videos, descriptions of practical exercises and laboratory work;
- information retrieval - study of Internet materials through a digest provided based on one's interests;
- FAQ (frequently asked questions) - search for answers to problems of interest through educational programs;
- Forum - exchange of views on science topics on telegram channels or distance learning platforms;
- Test-solving - consolidation of science module materials through exercises in instructional test programs;
- Preparation for the test - preparation for the expected interim and final examinations in the subject.
- Independent student work under the guidance of a traditional teacher (ORIWS):
- problem solving - solving problems on the topic of practical training and presenting it in writing;

- abstract - a written statement of the problem, in which literary sources are commented or scientific work, books are analyzed;
- Colloquium - a conversation to check the mastery of the theoretical part of the training module;
- essay - a written statement of personal opinion on a topical issue in a critical, journalistic and other genres;
- presentation - a slide and video presentation on a given topic;
- case-study - the search for solutions to problems in the production of tasks in the prescribed form;
- Work games - gaining professional skills by imitating professional processes, staging, role-playing;
- glossary - a brief explanation of terms on a given topic;
- group project - joint project work of 3-5 students;
- Calculations - graphs and calculations, usually based on the established guidelines for technical disciplines (engineering graphics, electrical engineering, information technology, etc.);
- course work - written and arithmetic work on the basis of established methodological guidelines on the problems of science or a set of disciplines (economics of enterprises, basics of management, ecology and environmental protection, civil protection, etc.);
- course project - calculations based on the established methodological guidelines, which are accompanied by graphic drawings on the problems of science or a set of disciplines (technical mechanics, technological processes and devices, disciplines related to the project);
- Diploma project - a project work on the design of a manufacturing enterprise or its subdivision on a given topic of the specialty, written on the basis of established guidelines, described by graphic drawings and calculations;
- Internship report - a report based on the established methodological guidelines for the internship (familiarization, production, undergraduate internships);
- Participation in science clubs - the student prepares visual aids in science clubs, such as models, slides, samples;
- participation in competitions - the student's participation in various competitions under the scientific guidance of the teacher ("Young Inventor", student startup projects, etc.);
- Participation in science Olympiads - participation in interdisciplinary Olympiads in science (chemistry, general chemical technology, physics, information technology, etc.);
- Presentations at scientific conferences - presentations at scientific and technical conferences on the topic of scientific research at universities, nationally and internationally;
- Publication of scientific theses and articles - publication of theses in scientific collections of scientific conferences and articles on scientific research in scientific journals;
- Participate in the preparation of teaching materials - participate in the preparation of textbooks, manuals, manuals, guidelines and other teaching materials.

Electronic media of IWS:

- Link - open an Internet link and comment on the material in the form of video or text;
- Chart - limited analysis of tables, diagrams and charts;
- Q / A - written answers to the questions asked by the teacher on the distance learning platform in the prescribed amount;

- Review - write an annotation to the source provided;
- SWOT - the student SWOT-analyzes a concept to a limited extent;
- Interview - a conversation on the study of the problem and upload it to the distance learning platform;
- Google Apps - collaboration on the Google Classroom platform to perform tasks in the form of slides, tables, texts;
 - Digest - a set of Internet links on a given topic, compiling a card index and a brief description of them;
 - Report - students submit their laboratory reports to a distance learning platform.

ORIWS are presented in the syllabus of the science by modules of science, indicating their description, topics, assignments, forms of conduct, the amount of hours. The content of IWS is determined by the nature of the subject, the technical capabilities of the university and the educational and methodological support of the library. IWS should be based on innovative technologies. The in-class form of ORIWS includes textbooks and primary resources for students, group assignments, and individual analytical activities. The ORIWS is held on a schedule for each subject throughout the academic year, indicating the date, time, audience, and tutors.

Classes in the framework of ORIWS can be in the form of consultations and interactive forms, the ratio of which is determined by the complexity of the subject, the amount of classroom time allocated for their study, the level of preparation of students.

The student, who receives individual counseling, signs a journal to record the work of teachers. The quality of IWS is controlled by the department, which approves the scope, content and type of reporting of IWS, determines the scope, sequence and deadlines for submission, reviews reports of students and teachers on the results of IWS.

REFERENCES

16. Djuraev, R. X., Turgunov, S. T., & Nazirova, G. M. (2013). Pedagogy. T.: O'zPFITI.
17. Nazirova, G., Yulchiboeva, D., & Khaydarov, O. (2021). The Main Factors of Formation and Development of Professional Competence of Teachers of Preschool Educational Organizations. *REVISTA GEINTEC-GESTAO INOVACAO E TECNOLOGIAS*, 11(3), 1698-1708.
18. Nazirova, G. M. (2017). Features of Organization Pedagogical Process in Preschool Educational Institutions. *Eastern European Scientific Journal*, (1).
19. Назирова, Г. М. (2014). РАЗВИТИЕ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ ВОСПИТАТЕЛЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЙ НА ОСНОВЕ СИСТЕМНОГО ПОДХОДА. *Актуальные проблемы современной науки*, (4), 96-99.
20. Назирова, Г. М. (2014). Особенности процесса деятельности воспитателей дошкольных образовательных учреждений. *Вопросы гуманитарных наук*, (4), 61-63.
21. ДЖУРАЕВА, Б., УМАРОВА, Х., ТОЖИБОЕВА, Х., & НАЗИРОВА, Г. ОСНОВЫ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ДОШКОЛЬНЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЙ.
22. Nazirova, G. M. INDICATORS FOR ENSURING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PEDAGOGICAL PROCESSES IN PRESCHOOL INSTITUTIONS.
23. Akilovna, E. M. (2022). THE COMPETENCE OF THE EDUCATOR IN THE APPLICATION OF TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE ORGANIZATION OF HEALTH CARE WORK FOR CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL AGE. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(04), 147-150.
24. Esonova, M. A. (2021). Improving the Preparation of Children for School Education on the Basis of the Curriculum in the Preschool System. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 18, 24-26.

25. Akilovna, E. M. (2021). Developing correct pronunciation in students through the formation of monologue speech in preschool education. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF DISCOURSE ON INNOVATION, INTEGRATION AND EDUCATION*, 2(2), 73-75.
26. Эсонова, М. А. (2016). ТАЪЛИМ МАЗМУНИНИНГ ИНТЕГРАЛ ХАРАКТЕРИ. In Сборники конференций НИЦ Социосфера (No. 6, pp. 98-101). Vedecko vydavatel'ske centrum Sociosfera-CZ sro.
27. ЭСОНОВА, М. А. (2015). ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ НРАВСТВЕННОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ У ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА. In Юность и Знания-Гарантия Успеха-2015 (pp. 335-337).
28. Эсонова, М. А. (2014). Роль речевой коммуникации в педагогическом мастерстве. In Теория и практика современных гуманитарных и естественных наук (pp. 164-167).
29. Эсонова, М. А. (2014). НАРОДНАЯ ПЕДАГОГИКА КАК ВЫСШАЯ СОЦИАЛЬНАЯ ЦЕННОСТЬ ДУХОВНОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ НАРОДА. In Исследование инновационного потенциала общества и формирование направлений его стратегического развития (pp. 296-299).
30. ЭСОНОВА, М. А., & ИБРАГИМОВА, Ш. А. (2014). ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ. In Будущее науки-2014 (pp. 132-136).
31. Melikuziyeva, M. (2021, December). Students' Independent and Creative Thinking through Practical Activities. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES* (Vol. 2, pp. 239-243).
32. Abduhafizovna, M. M., & Mirzoxid, Y. (2022). WAYS TO INCREASE THE LEGAL KNOWLEDGE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(02), 124-130.
33. Abdulkhafizovna, M. M. (2021). PECULIARITIES OF METHODS OF PEDAGOGICAL PSYCHOLOGY. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 2(10), 7-10.
34. Ashurova, G., Meliqo'ziyeva, M., & Karimova, S. (2019). REFORMS IN THE FIELD OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol, 7(12).
35. MUKHTASAR, I., & MAVLUDA, M. The Study of Projective Methods in Psychology. *JournalNX*, 7(02), 66-69.
36. Urinboyev, D. (2019). THOUGHTS ABOUT STRATAGEMA OF WESTERN AND EASTERN THINKERS. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 1(4), 147-151.
37. Burxonovich, D. B. (2022). SPIRITUAL TRAINING OF YOUNG ATHLETES. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(04), 144-146.
38. Jurayevich, H. A. (2020). Some issues of directing students for independent scientific research. *ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL*, 10(12), 1314-1317.
39. Tuxtasin, B., Rasuljon, S., & Xusanboy, R. (2021). Varieties of Industrial Robot Movement Trajectory. *Central Asian Journal Of Theoretical & Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 124-127.
40. Abdualiyevich, Z. M. (2021). THE ROLE OF PLAY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE PROCESSES IN CHILDREN. *Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT*, 1(11), 9-10.
41. Abdualiyevich, Z. M. (2021). CONTENT AND ESSENCE OF THE TOPIC" PSYCHOLOGY OF COMMUNICATION". *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(04), 300-305.
42. Abdualievich, Z. M. (2021). O 'Zbek xalq og 'zaki ijodining xususiyatlari. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF DISCOURSE ON INNOVATION, INTEGRATION AND EDUCATION*, 2(2), 338-340.

43. Zokirov, M. A. (2021). BOLALARDA BILISH JAROYONLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA O'YINNING AHAMIYATI. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 2(4), 465-470.
44. Inomovna, K. N. (2022). Principles of Educational Psychology and Pedagogy. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 5, 191-193.
45. Botirova, M. (2021, December). Secondary School Management: Technological Approach. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES (Vol. 2, pp. 244-247)*.
46. Botirova, M., & Seytsaliyeva, I. (2021). FORMATION OF THE ABILITY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS TO EVALUATE AND DIAGNOSE THE FUTURE PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY OF THE CHILD.
47. Kurbanova, M. (2021). Features Of Everyday Discourse In The English Language. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(4), 82-84.
48. Dilshoda Yusupova. (2021). THE USE AND SOCIO-LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF IDIOMS IN BUSINESS DISCOURSE. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(4), 71-73.
49. Каримова, Ш. Б. (2022). ОЗНАКОМЛЕНИЕ С НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫМИ АРХИТЕКТУРНЫМИ ПАМЯТНИКАМИ–КАК ИННОВАЦИОННЫЙ ФАКТОР ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ У ДЕТЕЙ ЛЮБВИ К РОДИНЕ. *Барқарорлик ва Етакчи Тадқиқотлар онлайн илмий журнали*, 2(1), 317-320.
50. Bahodirovna, A. Z. Pedagogical Bases Of Preparation Of Future Educators For Implementation Of Social Protection Of Children. *JournalNX*, 7(04), 399-402.
51. Yuldasheva, M., Nurmatova, M., & Tolipova, O. ADVANTAGES OF USING GAME TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION.
52. Ikromovna, T. O. (2022, April). THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVITY IN THE STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS AS AN URGENT PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM. In *E Conference Zone (pp. 301-303)*.
53. Ikromovna, T. O. (2022). SPECIFIC FEATURES OF DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVITY OF BACHELOR STUDENTS OF PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429*, 11(04), 17-20.
54. Kholmatova, Z. A. (2022). Forming a Culture of Dialogue-Based Relationships in Primary School Students is a Social Pedagogical Necessity. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 22, 288-291.
55. Холматова, З., & Хушназарова, М. (2014). Влияние интерактивных методов обучения на здоровье и развитие личности. *Инновационная экономика: перспективы развития и совершенствования*, (2 (5)), 280-285.
56. Холматова, З. А. (2016). ПСИХОДИДАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ У УЧАЩИХСЯ КУЛЬТУРЫ ДИАЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ. In *Образование через всю жизнь: непрерывное образование в интересах устойчивого развития (pp. 387-391)*.
57. Mirzamaxmudovna, X. J. N. (2022, April). PEDAGOGICAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF SOCIALIZATION OF EDUCATORS OF PRESCHOOL INSTITUTIONS. In *E Conference Zone (pp. 307-309)*.
58. Khojanazarova, N. (2022). The Essence of Socialization of Children in Preschool Educational Institutions On the Basis of a Systematic Approach. *World Bulletin of Social Sciences*, 7, 5-7.